

UNDERSTANDING TZVETAN TODOROV'S CONCEPTS ABOUT POETICS AND GENRE

Bhagwati Prasad

Research Scholar

University of Lucknow, Lucknow, U.P. India

Abstract

Tzvetan Todorov has emerged as a major thinker in humanities and social sciences over forty years. Todorov coined the term 'narratology' in 1969 for the scientific study of narrative. His early studies were exclusively about the theoretical dimensions of literature and narrative. In his book Genres in Discourse (1990), Todorov included an essay "The Origin of Genres" that aimed to point out different aspects of genres. Todorov begins this essay with a notion prevalent among most of the modern literary theorists. In the essay he insists that genres are neither static nor fixed but dynamic and ever changing. According to Todorov genres are the meeting place between general poetics and event -based literary history; as such, they constitute a privileged object that may well deserve to be the principal figure in literary studies. This way he outlines his strategy for constructing a theory of genres. He insists that this will be rooted in the particular genres, and will lead us towards a generalized concept of each genre. Todorov strictly follows the analytical procedure of Aristotle in his Poetics. Aristotle had taken up the genre of tragedy, identified its distinctive characteristics, while at the same time discussing philosophical concepts like 'mimesis' and 'catharsis'.

Key words: Tzvetan , Todorov's Concepts, narratology, genre, Poetics

INTRODUCTION

Tzvetan Todorov wrote his research dissertation under the supervision of Roland Barthes in the sixties. This was the decade when literary theory was emerging in France as an important discipline of study. Barthes, along with, A.-J. Greimas and Claude Levi-Strauss, was introducing and developing structuralism as an analytical method for the study of literature. These three theorists were particularly applying to literature the method outlined by the Swiss linguist Ferdinand de Saussure in his seminal work Course in General Linguistics. In his book Saussure had demonstrated that all cultural phenomena could be studied in terms of a limited number of sets of concepts. In his famous essay, 'An Introduction to the Structural Analysis of

Narrative,' Barthes had declared that the countless stories can be reduced to a finite number of plots. Something similar had been attempted in the thirties by the Russian Formalist Vladimir Propp in his *Morphology of the Folktale*.

Todorov was strongly influenced by these developments during his formative years. Consequently, his early writings were concerned with the formalist and structuralist projects of discovering the underlying principles of literature in general and of genres in particular. Aristotle had attempted the same in regard to the genre of tragedy in *Poetics*. However, in the sixties it was genuinely felt by literary theorists that Aristotle had made a beginning and there was the need for further exploration. Theorists like Barthes, Gerard Genette and Wayne C Booth led explorations of narrative. They were soon joined by Todorov, who coined the term 'narratology' in 1969 for the scientific study of narrative. His early studies were exclusively about the theoretical dimensions of literature and narrative.

REVIEW AND ANALYSIS

In *Genres in Discourse*, Todorov distinguishes between poetry as genre and poetics as a theory of genres, which according to him lays the theoretical foundation of studying literature. He writes: "Poetry is its own genre; poetics is the theory of genres." (Todorov 1990 15) Therefore, Todorov strictly follows the analytical procedure of Aristotle in his *Poetics*. Aristotle had taken up the genre of tragedy, identified its distinctive characteristics, while at the same time discussing philosophical concepts like 'mimesis' and 'catharsis'. Here Todorov appears to be clearly influenced by Russian Formalists who had declared that a study of theoretical foundations of literature entails delineation of the 'object of study'. Hence Todorov writes: Genres are the meeting place between general poetics and event -based literary history; as such, they constitute a privileged object that may well deserve to be the principal figure in literary studies. (Todorov 1990 19 – 20) In the above passage, Todorov outlines his strategy for constructing a theory of genres. He insists that this will be rooted in the particular genres, and will lead us towards a generalized concept of each genre.

A detailed consideration of Todorov's theory of genres is necessary to understand his ideas about literary theory, as it forms its cornerstone. In his book *Genres in Discourse* (1990), Todorov included an essay "The Origin of Genres" that aimed to point out different aspects of

genres. Todorov begins this essay with a notion prevalent among most of the modern literary theorists. In the essay he insists that genres are neither static nor fixed but dynamic and ever changing.

Todorov, however, builds on earlier concepts of genre, particularly those among the Greeks. It was in fact the Greeks who had pioneered genre theory and genre studies. The Greeks believed that an author's character and personality was directly responsible for the type of poetry he wrote. The Greek also believed that certain metrical forms were suited only to certain genres. In this regard Aristotle had declared:

We have, then, a natural instinct for representation and fortune and rhythm, and starting with these instincts men very gradually developed them until they produced poetry out of their improvisations. Poetry then splits into two kinds according to the poet's nature. For the more serious poets represented the noble deeds of noble man, while those of a less exalted nature represented actions of inferior men, at first writing satire just as the others wrote hymns and eulogies. (Farewell 383)

Indeed, this notion is a logical derivation from Plato's ideas about poetry. It also derives from his mimetic principle. Thus, exalted people will, in imitation of those exalted, perform noble deeds. The reverse will be the case with the lower types.

In his essay "The Origin of Genres," Todorov too emphasizes that the existence of distinctive genres in the days of classicism is acknowledged by all. Nobody questions the existence of ballad, ode, sonnet, tragedy, and comedy. However, Todorov raises a pertinent question. He asks whether ancient genres do exist today. And he answers in negative saying: "Even the genres of the nineteenth century, poetry or novel (and these are no longer quite a genre in our eyes), seem to be coming undone, at least in the literature 'that counts.'" (Todorov 1990, 13)

Todorov insists if a modern writes attempts to replicate a particular genre in modern times, he would lack authenticity. Thus, in his view, in today's world, one can say that the book is the only thing that matters, the book as it is, far from genres, outside the categorical

subdivisions – prose, poetry, novel, document. A book no longer belongs to a genre; every book stems from literature alone, without being modeled by generic conventions. Thus in modern times the distinctive genres have faded away losing their relevance. He quotes Maurice Blanchot in this article at times who also denies the existence of genres.

Todorov's ideas about genre can be fully understood only in the context of earlier theories of genre and their historical development. Ever since the late eighteenth century critics have been trying to find a theory of genre that would be more commensurate with the realities of individual texts within genres. The evolution of genre took many twists and turns through the nineteenth and twentieth century. It was heavily influenced by the philosophy of Wittgenstein and the poststructuralist concepts of relativity. In 1980, the instability engendered by these two new modes of thought came to a head in a paper written by Jacques Derrida titled "The Law of Genre". In the article, Derrida first articulates the idea that individual texts 'participate' in rather than 'belong' to certain genres. He does this by demonstrating that the "mark of genre" is not itself a member of a genre or type. Thus, the very characteristic that signifies genre defies classification. However, at the end of this essay, Derrida hints at what must be considered important and more fruitful a direction for genre theory. He writes: There, that is the whole of it; it is only what 'I' so that say, here kneeling at the edge of literature, can see. In sum the law. The law summoning: what 'I' can sight and what 'I' can say that I sight in this site of a recitation where I / we is. (Derrida 81)

Here, Derrida means that not only is taxonomy a subjective sport, but due to this very fact, the context and time of the taxonomical act deserves further study.

Another scholar J. Amy Devitt focuses on rhetorical genre. Most scholars recognize the restrictions placed on works that have been classified as a certain genre (for example Blanchot). However, viewing genre as a rhetorical device gives the author and the reader more freedom and "allows for choices." Amy writes:

Genres are not free-standing entities, but are actually intimately connected and interactive amongst them. Rhetorical genre recognizes that genres are generated by authors, readers, publishers, and the entire array of social forces that act upon a work at every stage of its production" (Amy 8).

This is a different conception from the earlier ideas, and has far reaching implications for genre theory. The originality of Todorov's concept of genre becomes immediately apparent when it is compared with the usual academic notions of genre.

The American critic M. H. Abrams, in his book *A Glossary of Literary Terms*, defines genre as "a term, French in origin, which denotes type or classes of literature." He further explains that "the genres into which literary works have been grouped at different times are very numerous, and the criteria on which the classifications have been based are highly variable." (Abrams 115)

Although it seems that genre should be easy to define, many scholars disagree on the finer points of textual categorization.

Todorov was certainly aware of the traditional notions of genre, but he reacted against them as he considered them outmoded and incapable of explaining developments in modern literature. That is why Todorov considers Blanchot's contribution to the study of genre in "The Origin of Genres." He states:

It's not that genres have disappeared, but the genres of the past have simply been replaced by others. We no longer speak of poetry and prose, documentary and fiction, but of novel and narrative, of narrative mode and discursive mode, of dialogue and journal. (Todorov 1990 14)

Todorov argues that a work can strictly not follow a genre, but this cannot be proved of non-existence of that particular genre itself. He says that this proves quite the contrary for two reasons. A genre is a set of pattern, and when a text disobeys laws of that genre, it does so against that pattern, and thereby asserts that genre itself. The existence of laws that are to be violated is a necessity for transgression to occur. Hence he asserts: "We might go even further and observe that the norm becomes visible – comes into existence – owing only to its transgression" (14). In his support, Todorov quotes Blanchot as follows:

It is true that Joyce shatters the novelistic form by making it aberrant; he also hints that form perhaps lives only through its alterations. It would develop not by engendering monsters,

formless, powerless works lacking in rigor, but by proving nothing but exceptions to itself, that constitute law and at the same time suppress it ... one has to think that every time, in these exceptional works where a limit is reached, the exception alone is what reveals to us that 'law', of which it also constitutes the unexpected and necessary deviation. It is thus as if, in the novelistic literature, and perhaps in all literature, we could never recognize the rule except by the exception that abolishes the rule, or more precisely, dislodges the center of which a certain work is the uncertain affirmation, the already destructive manifestation, the momentary, and soon-to-be negative presence (Quoted in Todorov 1990 14-15).

Thus Todorov advocates a dialectical concept of genre- it is to be categorized in terms of the deviations and aberrations. In turn it becomes essential to note that a work which is considered as an exceptional piece of writing necessarily proposes or presupposes a rule. And this is done by the moment it is recognized in its exceptional status. The work becomes a rule in turn, because of its commercial success and the critical attention it receives. Todorov takes readers back to the German Romantics and to Friedrich Schlegel in particular. In Friedrich Schlegel's writing, he discusses availability of certain Crocean assertion with the passages that tend in the opposite direction, establishing an equivalency between poetry and its genres. Certain things are no doubt common in both poetry and other arts like – representation, expression, and effect on the addressee. So, it can be said that poetry shares language use in common with everyday and scholarly language. Only the genres are its exclusive property, and therefore “the theory of poetic types would be the doctrine of art specific to poetry.” Thus he writes that “Poetry is its own genres; poetics is the theory of genres.” (15)

The title of the essay “The Origin of Genres” contains an implicit question: Where do genres come from? Todorov gives an answer that has far reaching consequences. He declares that ‘a genre comes from other genres.’ By this assertion Todorov implies that a new genre is always the transformation of an earlier one, or of several others by inversion, by displacement, and by combination. It is true that there has never been a literature without genres. It can be said here that literature is a system in constant transformation and, historically speaking, the question of origins cannot be separated from the terrain of the genres themselves. Todorov is however interested in discovering something that presides over the birth of a genre at a

particular time. He therefore writes: “The question of origin that I should like to raise ... We must begin by asking just what a genre is.” (16)

Todorov answers this question by examining the definition of genre. He says that the explanation that genres are classes of texts is insufficient and at times creates a misunderstanding. But this definition hardly conceals its nature behind the plurality the concept of genres call into play. Thus genre is a class, while literature is textual.

Todorov believes that it is actually discourse on genres that signals the historical existence of genres. But, perhaps, it would not be correct to conclude that genres are simply a metadiscursive notion and not discursive one. Todorov explains this with the help of a dominant genre in seventeenth century France, tragedy. One knows it in historical context usually, but according to him that does not mean that the tragedies themselves lack common features and that they could therefore not be described in other than historical terms. He points out that genres can be described from two different viewpoints –from that of empirical observation, and that of abstract analysis. In this way, Todorov is able to construct the context – historical and discursive- from within which he can provide a comprehensive definition of genre. Todorov explains that “in a given society, the recurrence of certain discursive properties is institutionalized, and individual texts are produced and perceived in relation to the norm constituted by that codification. A genre whether literary or not, is nothing other than the codification of discursive properties.” This is an entirely original manner of explaining what the concept of genre is. Thus, Todorov advances the idea that since, as it is widely accepted, that genres are models of writing for authors, genres exist as an institution. Therefore they function as “horizons of expectation” for readers. According to Todorov, genres communicate indirectly with the society where they are operative through their institutionalization. This aspect of genre study is the one that most interests the ethnological or the historian. Todorov suggests that one might establish the place of the notion of genre more precisely by making two symmetrical distinctions. He perceives genres as the historically attested codification of discursive properties. If genres are historically attested codification of discursive properties, it is easy to imagine the absence of either of the two components of the definition: historical reality and discursive reality. What happens, actually, in the absence of historical reality, one begins

dealing with the categories of general poetics that in turn depends upon textual level modes, registers, styles or even forms and manners. In the absence of discursive realities, one would be dealing with the notion that belong to literary history in the broad sense, such as trend, school, movement; or in other words, it can be called as “style”. He explains it thus: It is certain that literary movement that one knows as symbolism existed historically. But Todorov says that does not prove that the works of authors identified with symbolism have discursive properties in common. He states:

Genres are the meeting place between general poetics and event- based literary history, as such they constitute a privileged object that may well deserve to be the principal figure in literary studies. Our current descriptions of genres may be inadequate; that does not rule out impossibility of a theory of genres, and impossibility of a theory of genres, and the foregoing propositions are offered as preliminaries to such a theory. (19-20)

In A Glossary of Literary Terms, M.H Abrams writes: By many critics at present time, however, genres are conceived to be more or less arbitrary modes of classification, whose justification is their convenience in discussing literature (Abram 116). Similar ideas are expressed by Ralph Cohen in his essay “History and Genre.” He writes:

FINDINGS:

Genre concepts in theory and in practice arise, change, and decline for historical reasons. And since each genre is composed of texts that accrue, the grouping is a process, not a determinate category. Genres are open categories. Each member alters the genre by adding, contradicting, or changing constituents, especially those of members most closely related to it. The process by which genres are established always involves the human need for distinction and interrelation. Since the purposes of critics who establish genres vary, it is self-evident that the same texts can belong to different groupings of genres and serve different generic purposes (Cohen 204).

CONCLUSION

This approach to genre theory was the one most widely practiced. However, Todorov's concept of genre has transformed the traditional ideas of static form of literature. Todorov has demonstrated how his concept of genre stretches across the literary spectrum to explain the continuous transformation of literature and emergence of new literary forms.

REFERENCES

- Abrams, M. H. *A glossary of Literary Terms*. 8th ed. Delhi: Thomson Wordsworth, 2005.
- Amy, J. Devitt. *Writing Genres*. Carbondale: Southern Illinois University Press, 2004.
- Cohen, Ralph, ed. *New Directions in Literacy History*. Baltimore: The Johns Hopkins University Press, 1974. Ed. *The Future of Literary Theory*. London: Routledge, 1989.
- Derrida, Jacques. "The Law of Genre". *Critical Inquiry*. Autumn 1980: 55 – 87.
- "Genre" *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English*. 6th edition, 2000.
- Lodge, David, ed. *20th Century Literary Criticism: A Reader*. London: Longman, 1972.
- Todorov, Tzvetan. *Genres in Discourse*. Trans. Catherine Porter. Cambridge: CUP, 1990.